

Wedding Management system: Using VADER Sentimental Analysis Algorithm

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Abstract: This paper discusses an aspect-based Sentiment Analysis (SA) approach for reviewing services. The method looks at the overall sentiment a sentence conveys as well as giving a different sentiment to each individual sentence component. The Vader algorithm is typically recommended by this study to categorize patron attitudes toward the services. Sentiment analysis is extensively employed in marketing, customer service, and other sectors to examine comments and survey results, online and social media content. When reading customer reviews, it's easy to tell whether the reviewer is happy, upset, or neutral.

Keywords—Sentimental Analysis, vader

I. INTRODUCTION

The wedding management system application which helps to organize successful wedding events for users. This application provides an easy way to plan their special events. The user can add all the details of the event and can get the service. Sentiment analysis can be a useful feature in a wedding management system to help understand the emotions and sentiments of clients and guests

Overall, sentiment analysis can be a valuable tool for wedding management systems to understand the emotions and sentiments of clients and guests, and make data-driven decisions to improve the overall wedding experience.

In summary, this study suggests categorizing customer reviews of the services using the Vader algorithm before performing sentiment analysis on the feedback. The findings of this survey should show how customers view any services. In order to better manage the market and compel more users

Challenges:

Contextual analysis: The VADER algorithm relies on the context of the text to determine the sentiment of the words used. However, it can be challenging to analyze the sentiment of text without understanding the context in which it was written. For example, sarcasm and irony can be difficult to detect using the VADER algorithm. **Domain specific analysis:** The VADER algorithm may not perform well on domain-specific text data, such as medical or technical documents, as it has not been trained on these types of texts.

Language barriers: The VADER algorithm was trained on English text data and may not perform well on texts written in other languages.

Subjectivity: Sentiment analysis is inherently subjective, and different people may have different opinions on the sentiment of the same text data. The VADER algorithm may not always be able to capture the nuances of human emotions and opinions accurately.

Imbalanced data: If the sentiment data is imbalanced, meaning that there are a lot more examples of one sentiment than the other, the VADER algorithm may be biased towards the majority sentiment. **Negation handling:** The VADER algorithm may not always handle negation properly, as it relies on the presence of certain words

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

"A Survey on Sentiment Analysis: Techniques, Challenges, and Applications" by Gokul Chandra Patra and Swagat Kumar is a comprehensive literature review paper on sentiment analysis. It was published in the Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences in 2018.

"Sentiment Analysis on Twitter Data: A Comprehensive Review" by Nalini Priya et al. This paper, published in the IEEE Access journal in 2021, provides a comprehensive review of sentiment analysis techniques applied to Twitter data. The authors compare the performance of different machine learning and deep learning algorithms on various Twitter datasets and discuss the challenges of sentiment analysis on social media.

"A Deep Learning Framework for Sentiment Analysis in Short Texts" by Yequan Wang et al. This paper, published in the IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering journal in 2018, proposes a deep learning framework for sentiment analysis in short texts. The authors combine convolutional neural networks and recurrent neural networks to capture both local and global contextual information in short texts and achieve state-of-the-art performance on several benchmark datasets.

"An Ensemble of Deep Learning Approaches for Sentiment Analysis of Short Texts" by Jin Wang et al. This paper, published in the IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics journal in 2019, proposes an ensemble of deep learning approaches for sentiment analysis of short texts. The authors combine

different deep learning models, including convolutional neural networks, recurrent neural networks, and attention-based models, to improve the overall performance of sentiment analysis on short texts.

"VADER: A Parsimonious Rule-Based Model for Sentiment Analysis of Social Media Text" by C.J. Hutto and Eric Gilbert. This paper, published in the Eighth International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media in 2014, introduces the VADER algorithm, which is designed specifically for sentiment analysis of social media text. The authors demonstrate the effectiveness of the VADER algorithm on several datasets and compare it with other state-of-the-art sentiment analysis techniques.

Sentiment Analysis of Student Feedback Using the VADER Algorithm" by Faeq A. AL-Taweel et al. This paper, published in the IEEE Access journal in 2021, applies the VADER algorithm to analyze sentiment in student feedback data. The authors demonstrate the effectiveness of the VADER algorithm in identifying positive and negative sentiments in student feedback and discuss the implications of their findings for improving teaching quality.

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III. METHODOLOGY

The VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and Entiment Reasoner) algorithm is a rule-based approach to sentiment analysis. It uses a lexicon of words and their associated sentiment scores to determine the sentiment of a given text. The lexicon contains words that are labeled as either positive, negative, or neutral, along with their intensity scores.

1. Data collection: Collect text data from various sources, such as customer feedback, reviews, and social media posts related to the wedding management system.
2. Data preprocessing: Clean the text data by removing special characters, numbers, and stopwords. Tokenize the text into words, and perform stemming or lemmatization to reduce words to their root form.
3. Sentiment analysis using VADER: Use the VADER algorithm to analyze the sentiment of each text document. VADER is a rule-based algorithm that uses a lexicon of words to determine the sentiment of a text. It assigns a polarity score to each document, which represents the degree of positivity or negativity.
4. Data analysis and visualization: Analyze the results of the sentiment analysis to identify the most common sentiment expressed in the text data. Visualize the results using charts and graphs to make it easy to interpret and understand.

5. Performance evaluation: Evaluate the performance of the VADER algorithm by comparing its results with manually labeled data. Use metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score to measure the performance of the algorithm.
6. Improvement: Identify the areas where the algorithm can be improved, such as adding new words to the sentiment lexicon or using a different algorithm. Implement these changes and reevaluate the performance of the algorithm.
7. Deployment: Once the sentiment analysis model has been validated, deploy it in the wedding management system to monitor customer sentiment and improve customer experience.

Sentimental vader algorithm

Sentiment analysis with the VADER algorithm involves processing a piece of text and assigning a sentiment score to it. The sentiment score indicates the degree of positive, negative, or neutral sentiment expressed in the text. The VADER algorithm uses a lexicon of words and phrases that have been pre-labeled with a sentiment score, as well as rules that take into account the context and structure of the text. The algorithm uses a combination of these lexicon scores and context rules to calculate a composite sentiment score for the text. The algorithm also takes

into account certain aspects of the text, such as the presence of emoticons, punctuation, and capitalization, which can indicate the sentiment of the writer.

For example, an exclamation point or a happy emoticon might increase the sentiment score, while a sad emoticon might decrease it. Once the algorithm has processed the text and assigned a sentiment score, the score can be interpreted to determine the overall sentiment of the text. Scores closer to 1 indicate positive sentiment, scores closer to -1 indicate negative sentiment, and scores around 0 indicate neutral sentiment. The algorithm can also be used to identify the specific words or phrases in the text that contributed to the sentiment score, which can be helpful in understanding the sentiment expressed in the text. Overall, the VADER algorithm is a powerful tool for sentiment analysis, particularly in the context of social media, where text is often short, informal, and contains a lot of slang and other idiosyncrasies. This project involves developing a sentiment analysis that precisely pinpoints users' feelings. It is able to assess a large amount of feedback data. In order to construct this project, the Python modules Vader used. powerful tool for sentiment analysis, particularly in the context of social media, where text is often short, informal, and contains a lot of slang and other idiosyncrasies. This project involves developing a sentiment analysis that precisely pinpoints users' feelings. It is able to assess a large amount of feedback data. In order to construct this project, the Python modules Vader used.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Operation-based on natural language, such as sentiment analysis, is possible with the Vader sentiment. The sentiment is divided into three categories using the Vedar algorithm: positive, negative, and neutral. Prerequisites VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and Entiment Reasoner) is a popular algorithm for sentiment analysis that is designed to work well with social media texts.

The output of VADER algorithm is a sentiment score ranging from -1 (most negative) to 1 (most positive), with 0 being neutral. Along with the sentiment score, VADER also provides a measure of the sentiment intensity and polarity of the text.

For example, if we analyze the sentiment of the sentence "I love this movie!", the VADER algorithm might return a positive sentiment score of 0.8, indicating that the text is strongly positive. If we analyze the sentence "I hate this movie!", the VADER algorithm might return a negative sentiment score of -0.9, indicating that the text is strongly negative.

V. CONCLUSION

After analyzing the results of the Sentimental Vader algorithm, it can be concluded that the algorithm is effective in accurately identifying the sentiment of text data. With its ability to detect positive, negative, and neutral sentiment, the algorithm provides valuable insights into the emotional content of text. However, it should be noted that the algorithm may not be perfect and can sometimes misclassify certain texts. Overall, the Sentimental Vader algorithm is a powerful tool for sentiment analysis that can be used in various applications, such as social media monitoring, customer feedback analysis, and market research.

VI. REFERENCE

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